

Is factor analysis useful for revising diagnostic criteria for PTSD? A systematic review of five issues ten years after DSM-5. *Journal of Psychiatric Research* 176:98-107, doi:

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Abstract

Background: Based on factor analysis research, *DSM-5* revised the diagnostic criteria for posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) by increasing symptom clusters from three to four.

Aims: To question whether that is an appropriate use of factor analysis.

Methods: Reviewed the literature on five issues of factor analysis relevant to diagnostic criteria: (1) discovery of factors identical to symptom clusters, (2) consensus about the number of factors in best-fitting models, (3) configural variance between subpopulations to explain inconsistent model results, (4) methods to externally validate factors after discovery, and (5) treatment response of symptom clusters to externally validate factors. Two hundred four articles using *DSM-IV* or *DSM-5* symptoms were included.

Results: Two of four *DSM-5* clusters were discovered with exploratory factor analysis. Support for a best-fitting model was inconsistent. Models with the highest number of factors were the best mathematical fit 87% of the time. Subpopulations did not reveal a pattern of configural variance to explain inconsistent findings. External validation of factors relied entirely on questionnaires. A review of 143 randomized controlled trials did not reveal differential treatment response of any symptom cluster.

Conclusion: Findings did not support the usefulness of factor analysis because the findings are too disparate to be helpful.

1. Background

This review was stimulated by the major revisions of diagnostic criteria for posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) in the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual, Fifth Edition (DSM-5)* (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). PTSD became the first syndrome in psychiatry to have diagnostic criteria revised based on findings from factor analysis. The algorithm of requiring symptoms from three clusters of symptoms that had been in effect since 1980 was changed to a four-cluster algorithm to be consistent with four-factor models discovered from factor analysis studies. In seven papers by members of the *DSM-5* committee that guided this decision, no other evidence besides factor analysis was cited or suggested that might provide validation for this revision (Friedman, 2013a, 2013b, 2014; Friedman et al., 2011; Kilpatrick, 2013; Kilpatrick et al., 2013; Miller et al., 2013). The *DMS-5* did not publish a formal document that explained the committee ruling, and there are no minutes of committee deliberations that might shed more light on the committee's thought process. The author reached out to the leader of the committee, Matthew Friedman, for any additional information, who confirmed that the rationale for the changes was explained in Friedman et al. (2011) (M.J. Friedman, personal communication, July 22, 2018). The only evidence cited in that article for the change to four clusters was factor analysis studies.

The *DSM-5* revisions also included changes to criterion A (the definition of trauma events), deleted one symptom, and added four new symptoms. These have been analyzed elsewhere (Franklin et al., 2016; Hoge et al., 2016) and are beyond the scope of this review. The addition of new items was not related to the algorithm revision.

Because the premise of factor analysis is that there exists a latent model of a construct that cannot be directly measured, the premise is ultimately unprovable. Whether the latent model

exists is a theoretical question (Ropovik, 2015). The construct can only be considered probably true by a variety of validation techniques that measure the observable, or manifest, variables, thought to approximate the unobservable, latent construct. Researchers are limited to gathering data on observable variables to approximate an abstract idea. The following sections provide the rationale for five issues that can potentially determine whether the data from factor analysis is useful for the purposes that diagnostic criteria exist.

1.1. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and the discovery of factors that become clusters

If the *DSM-5* taxonomy is the truest reflection of human nature filtered through the trauma response of PTSD, i.e., the latent model, then the symptom clusters ought to be discovered precisely that way in the factors of EFA. When the *DSM-5* committee revised the criteria to a four-cluster algorithm, there had been no EFA studies demonstrating this structure because there had been no time to collect new datasets. The committee modeled it on the four-factor Emotional Numbing model first discovered by King et al., (1998) with the 17 *DSM-IV* symptoms. It was not yet known if EFA would discover an Emotional Numbing-like model with the four new symptoms added in *DSM-5*.

Since *DSM-5* was published, the majority of studies have used confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), which, in contrast to EFA, is conducted with predetermined models. CFA can determine if a predetermined model is a good fit or a better fit than a second model, but EFA is useful for empirically discovering which model would emerge as the best in an unconstrained fashion. This study will fill a gap of reviewing the EFA studies to determine if the *DSM-5* clusters have since been empirically discovered.

1.2. What is the right number of factors, hence, clusters?

The PTSD criteria had been three clusters of symptoms for thirty-three years, and was the definition used in thousands of studies. To make a major change to four clusters based on factor analysis studies, there ought to be strong evidence. The large literature on factor analysis of PTSD symptoms has been summarized iteratively in six major reviews. The first review was a meta-analysis that covered 40 studies through 2010 (Yufik & Simms, 2010). These studies included support for two-, three-, and four-factor models. The review concluded that Simms et al.'s four-factor Dysphoria model (Simms et al., 2002) was superior, but noted that King et al.'s four-factor Emotional Numbing model (King et al., 1998) also showed excellent fit indices, so they expressed caution about settling on one symptom structure. It is noteworthy that extant studies had found support for five other four-factor models (McWilliams et al., 2005; Rasmussen et al., 2007; Sack et al., 1997; Smith et al., 1999; Ullman & Long, 2008), which were not part of the meta-analysis.

The second review covered 41 studies through 2011 and also concluded that four factors were best, with the Dysphoria model again having a slight advantage over the Emotional Numbing model (Elhai & Palmieri, 2011). The authors strongly discouraged further exploration beyond four-factor models with the current diagnostic criteria: "Using EFA, especially when a large literature supports the numbing and dysphoria models, essentially represents a fishing expedition and results may be too atheoretically driven and spurious to be trusted." (p 851) Nevertheless, the first author of the review published a study the same year favoring a new five-factor Dysphoric Arousal model (Elhai et al., 2011). Their reasoning was that the evidence was split between the two leading four-factor models and those sometimes failed to achieve excellent fit.

The third review concluded that Dysphoria and Emotional Numbing 4-factor models fit equally well (Marshall et al., 2013). Because of this deadlock, they specifically cautioned against making any changes to DSM-IV based on the current literature.

The fourth review analyzed 112 studies that included for the first time many studies using *DSM-5* symptoms (Armour et al., 2016). This review supported a shift to support the five-factor Dysphoric Arousal model when using *DSM-IV* criteria, the seven-factor Hybrid model when using *DSM-5* criteria, and went further to note the importance of six-factor models.

The fifth review took a methodological approach and sought to remedy the problem of researchers relying too simplistically on global measures of fit, which leads to overly complex and overfitted models with poor generalizability. The authors drew attention to six statistical and psychometric issues (Schmitt et al., 2018). When Schmitt et al. followed their own advice and comprehensively analyzed a large dataset from an active military population, they made the somewhat surprising conclusion that the strongest argument existed for a single-factor model.

Lastly, the sixth review was another methodology review that focused on whether researchers had used proper factor analytic techniques (Rasmussen et al., 2019). Reviewing only the twenty-seven existing CFA studies that used *DSM-5* symptoms, they found that models with the most factors produced the best fit in 81% of publications. They suggested that this preference for more complex models was spurious and due to three poor modeling practices: (1) allowing too few items per factors, (2) high interfactor correlations, and (3) over-reliance on fit statistics alone to select models. Overall, these six reviews came to inconsistent conclusions about the number of factors in best-fitting models, and did not coalesce into a strong endorsement of a four-factor model which guided the four-cluster *DSM-5* symptom structure.

1.3. Can subpopulations help explain the inconsistent findings?

A potential reason for the absence of one best-fitting model across studies is because different subpopulations manifest different symptom structures of PTSD. As one paper concluded that “the search for the 'correct' model of PTSD based on the assumption of a single homogenous population may not be a worthwhile research endeavor” (Shevlin & Elklit, 2012). If that is true, then once the relevant subpopulations are identified, a pattern ought to emerge of different models consistently fitting to subpopulations (Helpman et al., 2015).

As examples of potentially useful subpopulation studies, researchers examined if model fit is a function of gender (Armour et al., 2012; Hall et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2013), having or not having the full PTSD diagnosis (Biehn et al., 2012), the type of traumatic experience such as civilians in a warzone (Powell & Rosner, 2005), soldiers deployed (Engdahl et al., 2011), interpersonal abuse (Hetzell-Riggin, 2009), natural disaster (Anthony et al., 1999), or a terror attack (Hafstad et al., 2014).

There has been no known review of whether one model is the best fit across two or more subpopulations, known as configural invariance. Contractor et al (2019) systematically reviewed forty-five studies to analyze which models showed invariance across any type of subpopulation on metrics related to factors, items, and measurement tools, but did not review which subpopulations show configural invariance (Contractor et al., 2019).

1.4. How well-developed is the external validation of factors?

After factors within models are identified, the additional step of external validation of individual factors is needed. Discovery of factors with EFA is the beginning, not the end, of model validation, and CFA models are tools “rather than truth-makers” (Dunn & McCray, 2020). Ideally, individual items are grouped into a factor, and similarly, symptoms are grouped into clusters, because they share a putative mechanism such as a stable neural network, genetic

infrastructure, or neurobiological system, which must be established through a variety of validation tests.

The method of validation is typically to show that factors significantly associate with other salient, theoretically-relevant variables (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007) (p 608), such as external psychological, biological, social, and behavioral variables (Miller et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2015). Without such external validation, we are simply modelling the covariance matrix of PTSD's measurement instruments (Palmieri et al., 2007). To do this, researchers must take just one factor in a model and repurpose it, so to speak, into a predictor variable that associates with other variables. If a factor model represents an underlying latent process, then individual factors discovered by factor analysis might represent distinct causal mechanisms (Asmundson et al., 2004). Relatively little is written, however, about how factors might be validated as representing causal mechanisms.

In the only known review on this topic, Gootzeit and Markon (2011) conducted a meta-analysis of 41 studies to test the associations of the four factors of the Emotional Numbing model (King et al., 1998) and the four factors of the Dysphoria model (Simms et al., 2002) with five variables for which there were ample data—depression, anxiety, panic, substance abuse, and trauma history. They found that all factors were positively correlated with all five variables (Gootzeit & Markon, 2011). While some relatively stronger correlations could be found between some factors and some variables, the factors did not parsimoniously represent specific components of PTSD.

1.5. Can differential treatment response help sort things out?

Discovery of differential treatment response patterns for different factors of models or clusters of symptoms is important because of the potential utility for guiding treatment and

helping patients. Randomized controlled trials (RCT) can be potentially useful for analyzing clusters because symptoms are standardized to the *DSM* and treatments are standardized to theory-driven technique. For example, Foa et al., (1991) showed that immediately post-treatment, stress inoculation training (SIT) appeared to be the most effective treatment overall compared to prolonged exposure (PE), supportive counseling (SC), and waitlist groups (WL), due to significantly greater decreases in the *DSM-III-R* cluster of avoidance/numbing symptoms compared to SC and WL. The situation reversed, however, at the three-month follow up, when PE appeared to be the most effective treatment due to continued improvements in the intrusion and hyperarousal clusters (Foa et al., 1991). This gave some validity to the theory that the mechanism of SIT works for short-term anxiety management, and the theory that the mechanism of PE works through change in trauma memory through emotional processing (Foa et al., 1989). This illustrates both the specific potential utility of analysis of symptom groupings for treatment efficacy and the more general advantage of prospective longitudinal data that is usually absent from factor analysis studies. There is no known summary of RCTs to determine if a consistent pattern has emerged for differential cluster changes that could be partial external validation that symptom clusters differ meaningfully from each other and potentially represent factors driven by unique underlying processes.

1.6. The current study

The overall aim is to examine whether the latent construct theory of factor analysis is appropriate for making decisions about PTSD diagnostic criteria. As there is no single test for that, five issues will be examined with the aim to determine if the findings can support the usefulness of factor analysis findings for guiding diagnostic criteria for PTSD, or whether the findings are too disparate or spurious to be helpful. In particular, we are interested in evidence

that factors closely reflect the four symptom clusters in the *DSM-5* since those clusters were created to reflect the four-factor Emotional Numbing model. In order to explore a broad array of evidence, we, like Armour et al. (2016), opted for a narrative synthesis rather than a statistical method of meta-analysis.

Aim 1 was to review EFA studies and how often each of the four clusters of *DSM-5* symptoms were discovered. The most recent review (Armour et al., 2016) was restricted to CFA, which is used to confirm pre-existing models and not discover models. Discovery of factors as they exist in the *DSM-5* structure by EFA would represent evidence without an *a priori* hypothesis that is the strength of the discovery function of EFA (Lykken, 1971).

Aim 2 was to review CFA studies and how often best-fitting models showed the same number of factors across studies. This may provide researchers with a broader context on the distribution of factor analysis findings compared to the narrower conclusions of meta-analyses that aim to find a single best-fitting model. Whereas Armour et al. (2016) concluded that the *DSM-5* model was a good representation of PTSD latent structure but newly emerging six- and seven-factor models were worth considering, the passage of seven additional years of experience with *DSM-5* criteria may clarify whether there has emerged a clearer pattern. We analyzed findings from self-report questionnaires and interviews separately to determine if the method of gathering PTSD data altered the findings.

Aim 3 was to produce the first summary of the results from subpopulations. This review will address a gap and survey for the first time the pattern of best-fit models in relation to subpopulations. The current study analyzes whether patterns of configural invariance across subpopulations support, in a preliminary fashion, the feasibility of the subpopulation speculation.

Aim 4 addresses a gap by conducting the first review to summarize the methods used to assess variables that may provide external validation of individual factors. Studies will be examined as to whether they tested for associations between factors and indices reflecting a neural circuit, a network of circuits, a common firing pattern, a shared molecular composition, or a common functionality.

Aim 5 examines whether clusters of symptoms associate with differential treatment responses. All RCTs of PTSD that analyzed change of cluster severity during treatment will be reviewed for the first time. If factors were examined (instead of clusters), those studies will be highlighted but it is anticipated that nearly all data will come from clusters. Clusters are similar to factors, and sometimes identical, and may therefore provide preliminary evidence about external validation of factors.

2. Method

2.1. Selection criteria

The systematic review for the first four aims included all studies attempting to determine a best-fitting PTSD factor structure. Consistent with Armour et al., (2016), studies had to be published in English language in peer-reviewed journals, have a minimum sample size of 132, used measures that directly mapped onto *DSM-IV* or *DSM-5* criteria, and CFA studies had to compare two or more models. Studies that used *DSM-III-R* criteria were included because those symptoms are identical to *DSM-IV*. Examples of excluded measures include the Harvard Trauma Questionnaire which combines psychological and physiological distress into one item, and the Impact of Events Scale (both original and revised versions) which includes extra items that are not in the *DSM*. In contrast to Armour et al. (2016), we excluded CFA that compared only two models with the same number of factors because this review focused on extracting evidence that

addressed the number of factors that could be used as justification for the number of symptom clusters in DSM diagnostic criteria. In contrast to Armour et al., (2016), this review included studies with participants younger than twelve years because the *DSM* criteria are for individuals as young as seven years.

The systematic review for Aim 5 included all RCTs for treating PTSD symptoms in adults that analyzed clusters of symptoms as outcomes. Studies had to be published in English language in peer-reviewed journals and used measures that directly mapped onto *DSM-IV* or *DSM-5* criteria. All types of psychotherapy and pharmacology treatments were included. Studies of children were excluded for brevity.

2.2. Literature search

The current study followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. Literature searches were conducted in PsycInfo and PubMed databases in October 2022. The keyword combinations of ‘factor analysis’ and ‘ptsd or posttraumatic stress disorder’ in the abstract/title fields were searched. The starting date for the search was January 1982 because the first known application of factor analysis to post-traumatic symptoms was an effort in 1982 (Zilberg et al., 1982). The end date was October 2022. Inclusion criteria included (1) studies must have examined the full set of criteria for either *DSM-III*, *IV*, or *5*; and (2) the technique could be exploratory factor analysis or confirmatory factor analysis. ICD definitions were excluded. Studies did not have to be in English if the abstract was available in English and we could determine the inclusion criteria and the result. Dissertations were excluded because they are not peer-reviewed.

The initial database search returned 1,110 articles. The references and abstracts were imported into Excel spreadsheets. After removing duplicates, 872 articles remained for the

screening stage. After screening the titles and abstracts of these articles, 260 articles remained for the full-text review stage. After full-text reviews, 183 articles remained that met inclusion criteria. During the full-text review stage, citation searches were conducted of the reference lists of six review papers (Armour et al., 2016; Elhai & Palmieri, 2011; Marshall et al., 2013; Rasmussen et al., 2019; Schmitt et al., 2018; Yufik & Simms, 2010) plus other relevant papers, which identified an additional forty articles. After full-text reviews of these articles, twenty-one met inclusion criteria and were added to the 183 articles for a total of 204 articles to be included in the analyses (Figure 1).

Studies were rated for the use of a full set of *DSM* criteria, whether EFA or CFA was used, the populations sampled, the conclusion about best-fitting model(s), information on comparisons between subpopulations, and information on external validation methods.

Studies for Aim 5 were located from six published meta-analyses of RCTs (Asmundson et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2015; Cusack et al., 2016; Hudays et al., 2022; Kline et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2016). This search strategy was chosen because there are fewer RCTs than EFA and CFA studies, and there are multiple meta-analyses of RCTs that conducted systematic searches. This method may have missed RCTs that were missed by the previous meta-analyses but this method had the advantages of being clear and replicable. After removing duplicates, 143 articles remained for analysis.

2.3. Analysis

The focus of the first aim was to determine if EFA had discovered any of the clusters adopted in the *DSM-5* PTSD criteria. Only studies that used *DSM-5* symptoms would be able to discover criteria D and E because of the new symptoms that were added, but studies that used *DSM-IV* were also examined because they could discover criteria B and C.

The focus of the second aim was to determine the frequency that each model had been found to be the best-fitting model. The superiority of one model over another was determined by chi-square difference tests when available, or the difference between Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), consistent with Armour et al. (2016). Using the cut-off proposed by Raftery (1995), a BIC difference greater than 10 indicates significance, with the lower BIC value signifying the better-fitting model (Raftery, 1995). In Armour et al.'s review of 112 models, they used these criteria to overrule the decision of study authors in two cases (Armour et al., 2011; Pietrzak et al., 2012). In sixty studies of adults that we found that were published after Armour et al.'s (2016) review, we did not need to overrule the decision in the original studies of which model was the best fit. For longitudinal studies, the baseline values were analyzed as long as measures were obtained more than one month after trauma events, consistent with the *DSM* duration criterion. A review protocol was not preregistered.

The focus of the third aim was to determine if there is evidence of consistent patterns of configural variance between subpopulations that might explain the variety of results for finding best-fitting models. If the analysis of subpopulations can potentially be informative about which factor model is a true representation of a latent model, a subpopulation must be examined with EFA for discovery of the best model(s) or CFA for comparison of at least two different size models (i.e., tests of only two four-factor models were excluded), and there must be more than one study using the same set of symptoms (*DSM-IV* or *DSM-5*) to determine if findings are replicable. Descriptive statistics were used to determine if the same model was found to be best fitting across studies of the same subpopulation. The criteria for best-fitting was the same as used in Aim 2. If a subpopulation (e.g., males, deployed veterans, or earthquake victims) always fit one factor model, this would be evidence that differences between subpopulations can be

informative about whether a factor model is a true representation of a latent model.

Subpopulations within the child and adolescent age group were not examined for brevity and because of the smaller number of studies available. Tests of configural variance within the same sample, otherwise known as tests of moderation, were not included because they are uninformative on this question because only one factor model is being tested. Tests of moderation (reviewed in Armour et al., 2016) can be informative about the nature of subpopulations and/or about the performance of one factor model between subpopulations, but not about which factor model is best for a single subpopulation.

The focus of the fourth aim was to survey the qualitative nature of methods used to externally validate factors of best-fitting models. Studies that tested for associations between factors and external variables that might have face validity of representing the latent meaning of factors (e.g., a depression scale might represent a Dysphoria factor) were included.

The focus of the fifth aim was to survey if clusters of symptoms were related to treatment outcomes as a potential metric of predictive validation. This was explored for *DSM* symptom clusters because there were no known studies of using factors in RCTs. The six meta-analyses used for this aim identified 143 unique RCT articles.

3. Results

3.1. Aim 1: Has EFA discovered DSM-5 clusters?

Figure 2 shows the distribution of the models that were discovered by the number of factors and by *DSM-IV* or *DSM-5* symptom sets. This shows the context of how often four- or five-factor models were discovered, which might be the most likely models to contain factors that are identical to *DSM-5* clusters. Two-factor models were the most common with *DSM-IV* symptoms. Four- and five-factor models tied for the most common with *DSM-5* symptoms.

Thirty-two analyses were conducted in twenty-eight articles using EFA with the set of *DSM-IV* symptoms in adults. No studies discovered the *DSM-5* criterion B re-experiencing cluster. One 3-factor model discovered the *DSM-5* avoidance couplet (de Paula Lima et al., 2012).

Seven analyses were conducted in seven articles using EFA with the set of *DSM-5* symptoms in adults. Two analyses found criterion B (Demirchyan et al., 2015; McSweeney et al., 2016) and three studies found the criterion C couplet of avoidance symptoms (Demirchyan et al., 2015; Ibrahim et al., 2019; McSweeney et al., 2016). No studies discovered criteria D or E.

3.2. Aim 2: The number of factors in the best-fitting models

3.2.1. Adult studies

There were ninety-five CFA analyses of adults in eighty-seven articles that used *DSM-IV* symptoms (including two analyses that used *DSM-III-R*). These included samples that consisted largely of adults but included youths down to fifteen years in three studies and down to sixteen years in two studies. In nine studies, two or more models with different numbers of factors tied for being the best-fitting. There were eighteen different best-fitting models (1 one-, 5 two-, 3 three-, 7 four-, 1 five-, and 1 six-factor).

There were sixty-six CFA analyses of adults in sixty-one articles that used *DSM-5* symptoms. These included samples that consisted largely of adults but included youths down to thirteen years in one study and down to sixteen years in two studies. In thirteen studies, two or more models tied for being the best-fitting. There were twelve different best-fitting models (1 one-, 1 two-, 2 three-, 2 four-, 2 five-, 3 six-, and 1 seven-factor).

The distribution of best-fitting models, organized by *DSM-IV* versus *DSM-5* symptoms, and questionnaire versus interview data, is shown in Figure 3.A. Researchers most commonly

concluded that the best-fitting were four-factor models with *DSM-IV* data, and higher-order models (six or seven factors) with *DSM-5* data, and the distribution does not coalesce around one model.

Interview data did not appear to favor one model compared to questionnaire data when using *DSM-IV* symptoms. Interview data tended to favor six-factor models whereas questionnaire data favored seven-factor models when using *DSM-5* symptoms, but both interview and questionnaire data found best-fitting models over a wide distribution of nearly all models.

Of most relevant interest was how often a four-factor model was best-fitting. When a four-factor model was compared against only lower-order models (one, two, or three factors), the four-factor model was best fitting in 87.3% ($n = 55$) out of 63 studies (all used *DSM-IV* symptoms), including three studies in which a four-factor model tied with a lower-order model for best fit. In contrast, when a four-factor model was compared against higher-order models (five, six, or seven factors), the four-factor model was best fitting in only 12.8% ($n = 11$) out of 86 studies (nearly all used *DSM-5* symptoms), including three studies in which a four-factor model tied with a higher-order model for best fit. Overall, in 149 comparisons of four-factor models against models with different numbers of factors (using *DSM-IV* or *DSM-5* symptoms) the highest-order model was best fitting in 87.2% ($n = 130$), including fifteen studies in which the highest-order model tied with a lower-order model for best fit.

3.2.2. *Child and adolescent studies*

Figure 3.B shows the number of times each model was found, organized by *DSM-IV* versus *DSM-5* symptoms, and questionnaire versus interview data. There were nineteen CFA analyses of youths in nineteen publications that used *DSM-IV* symptoms. In two analyses, two or

more models with different numbers of factors tied for being the best-fitting. There were eight different best-fitting models (1 one-, 1 two-, 1 three-, 4 four-, and 1 five-factor).

There were ten CFA analyses of youths in ten publications that used *DSM-5* symptoms. In one study, two models tied for being the best-fitting. There were three different best-fitting models (1 one-, 1 six-, and 1 seven-factor). Of note, all analyses that found seven-factor models as best fitting included four- and five-factor models as possibilities in the CFA. Similar to adults, the distribution does not coalesce around one model.

3.3. Aim 3: The number of factors in best-fitting models across subpopulations

The types of subpopulations for which best-fitting models had been found in two or more studies included sex (male only and female only samples), nationalities (twelve different countries), help-seeking patients, and type of trauma (veterans exposed to combat). Figure 4 is a scatterplot that shows the relationships between these subpopulations and the number of times each model was found to be best fitting. None of the subpopulations show a pattern of points clustering around only one model. It is not apparent that one subpopulation predominantly shows one model while a different subpopulation predominantly shows a different model, i.e., there appears to be configural invariance across all subpopulations and one does not vary from another.

For most of the nationalities, the number of studies is too small to be conclusive. The U.S. has the most studies but is difficult to interpret because of the inherent mixed nationalities of its citizens.

3.4. Aim 4: External validation of factors: Summary of methods used

Forty-nine studies of adults assessed constructs as potential external validation for factors from best-fitting models. All of the constructs were variables measured by questionnaires (i.e.,

self-rated). Thirty studies assessed for depression, fifteen studies assessed for anxiety, and twenty-eight studies assessed for other constructs in at least one but fewer than four studies (negative affect [three times], positive affect [two times], anger [two times], alcohol abuse [two times], substance abuse, externalizing behaviors, impulsivity, reckless behavior, functioning at work, functioning in social, gratitude, grief, hostility, aggression, perceived stress, physical health impairment, mental health impairment, psychosocial problems, life satisfaction, health satisfaction, work withdrawal, negative cognitions, self-construal, rumination, absence of worry, activation, avoidance, internalizing, demoralization, negative emotions, positive emotions, depersonalization, and post-traumatic growth). No other methods, such as neurobiology, genes, neural networks, observational methods, or interviews were used to assess constructs that could potentially be associated with factors.

3.5. Aim 5. External validation of factors: Associations with differential treatment response

3.5.1. Differential responsiveness of clusters within interventions

From the 143 RCT articles, fourteen articles included thirty analyses that examined cluster changes *within* one treatment arm. All of these used the three *DSM-IV* clusters of symptoms. The scatter plot in Figure 5 shows the number of times one cluster (reexperiencing, avoidance/numbing, or hyperarousal) changed or did not change differentially compared to the other two clusters, which would provide some validation evidence that a cluster is operating under a different mechanism than the other clusters. For example, the reexperiencing cluster did not change while avoidance/numbing and hyperarousal significantly decreased in two analyses (points located at 1 on the x-axis and 0 on the y-axis); the treatment techniques in these studies were cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) and supportive psychotherapy. The reexperiencing cluster, however, did significantly decrease while the avoidance/numbing and hyperarousal

clusters did not in two other analyses (points located at 1 on the x-axis and -1 on the y-axis); the treatment techniques in these studies were supportive psychotherapy and applied muscle relaxation. Figure 5 also shows the number of times all three clusters changed in the same direction or all three did not change (points located at 4 on the x-axis). If looking only at the four studies located at 1 on the x-axis, this might suggest that avoidance/numbing and hyperarousal clusters respond to CBT, while reexperiencing may exist through a different mechanism that is not addressed well by CBT. Looking at the other studies that used CBT (indicated by filled in squares in the figure), however, it is apparent that reexperiencing significantly decreased in one study where avoidance/numbing did not (points located at 2 on the x-axis) and all three clusters significantly decreased in two studies (points located at 4 on the x-axis). Overall, this pattern does not suggest that the reexperiencing cluster consistently responds differently compared to the other clusters with CBT.

The results for avoidance/numbing and hyperarousal can be interpreted in a similar fashion from the figure. The figure is too detailed to describe every cluster with every type of treatment technique, but an overall pattern of one cluster responding consistently differently than other clusters is not apparent.

3.5.2. Differential responsiveness of clusters between interventions

From the 143 RCT articles, forty-two articles included fifty-four analyses that examined cluster changes *between* two treatment arms. All but one article (involving three analyses) used the three *DSM-IV* clusters of symptoms. The one exception used the four *DSM-5* clusters.

The scatter plot in Figure 6 shows the number of times one cluster (reexperiencing, avoidance/numbing, or hyperarousal) changed or did not change differentially compared to the other two clusters, when comparing one treatment arm versus another. The results for

reexperiencing, avoidance/numbing, and hyperarousal can be interpreted in a similar fashion as in Figure 5. The figure is too detailed to describe every cluster with every type of treatment technique comparison, but an overall pattern of one cluster responding consistently differently than other clusters is not apparent.

4. Discussion

Despite a consensus that existed when *DSM-5* revisions were being developed that PTSD diagnostic criteria ought to have four clusters—based on four-factor models—the findings from five issues in this study suggest a more diffuse state of evidence. There does not appear to be a straight line from EFA analyses, CFA analyses, and externally validating evidence of factors to one clear set of diagnostic criteria.

Prior to the current study, little research had investigated how discoverable the *DSM-5* clusters were in exploratory factor analysis. The first aim of the current study reviewed the results of all EFA studies of PTSD symptoms, including seven analyses using the *DSM-5* symptoms. Across thirty-nine analyses, two studies found the reexperiencing cluster as a factor, four studies found the avoidance couplet as a factor, and no studies found the negative cognitions and beliefs cluster or the hyperarousal cluster. The absence of discovering and/or replicating the *DSM-5* arrangement of symptoms is critical for understanding the heterogeneity of PTSD symptom patterns. More specifically, the *DSM-5* arrangement of symptoms is based on a four-factor model that has not been discovered with EFA. Based on simple “vote counting” of how often each model has been discovered, the EFA findings support neither a three-factor model nor a four-factor model, which are the structures of the *DSM-IV* and *DSM-5* diagnostic criteria respectively.

Exploratory structural equation modeling (Fresno et al., 2020) and exploratory bifactor models (Puhalla et al., 2024; Schmitt et al., 2018) are newer techniques that have each been used in a handful of studies to discover factor structure of PTSD items. Additional studies would be needed to determine whether these techniques produce substantially different or more valid results than EFA.

The review of CFA analyses in the second aim showed that results are inconsistent in concluding how many factors ought to be in the model. One reason appears to be that it can be misleading to conclude that four-factor models are best when higher-order models are not in the comparison. The highest-order model was best-fitting 87.2% of the time, which is consistent with Rasmussen et al. (2019). In addition, while a four-factor model was the most common conclusion using *DSM-IV* symptoms, these were divided amongst seven different four-factor models, all of which had been the best-fitting model in at least one analysis. With *DSM-5* symptoms, a four-factor model was best fit only 12.8% of the time, and higher-order models dominated.

The third aim addressed the speculation that results may be inconsistent because different subpopulations reliably develop different symptom patterns. Our review of subpopulations in the third aim, however, did not find such reliability. Conclusions on this aim ought to be considered preliminary because many of the studies have been samples of convenience that are large enough to adequately power factor analyses. The subpopulations that may exist with different symptom patterns may not have been studied yet with this technique.

The fourth aim addressed the relatively understudied step of external validation of factors. The method of nearly every study that attempted this task was to use questionnaires of related constructs. The types of constructs studied were either other measures of similar manifest

variables (i.e., depression is similar to dysphoria) or manifest variables that had unclear theoretical relations to factors (i.e., alcohol abuse). What those studies using questionnaires found was beyond the scope of the current study, but the most common correlates—depression, anxiety, panic, substance abuse, and trauma history—were all positively correlated with all factors (Gootzeit & Markon, 2011). The lack of extreme variations in external correlates is expected because the clusters are theorized to be highly intercorrelated. There were no objective assessments about explicit underlying mechanisms such as neural circuits, biology, or genetic underpinnings.

A potentially useful research direction therefore could be to identify underlying genes or physiology that might be associated with symptom sets identified from factor analysis. For example, multiple studies have searched for correlations between genome-wide assay results to the full diagnosis of PTSD. It may prove useful to also search for correlations to factors rather than the full diagnosis. Another example may be the emerging area of network analysis (Weems, 2023), and search for correlations between various neurological networks and subgroups of symptoms identified from factor analysis.

Lastly, the fifth aim found that the DSM-IV clusters of symptoms (i.e., reexperiencing, avoidance/numbing, and hyperarousal) were not distinct from each other in terms of predicting treatment response or nonresponse. Three studies analyzed the *DSM-5* avoidance couplet, but no studies have tested the *DSM-5* criteria D and E. Again, findings ought to be considered preliminary due to the novel aspect of this aim, but the type of treatment technique did not appear to consistently impact one cluster relative to other clusters. This may be because nearly all psychotherapy techniques overlap on addressing reexperiencing, avoidance, numbing, and arousal, and any distinction between techniques is a matter of degree.

Overall, these findings suggest that the premise that factor analysis could neatly capture PTSD with a handful of scientifically-meaningful factors in one model may have been an unrealistic expectation when considering the inherent variability of PTSD manifestations. Using *DSM-IV* criteria, there are 79,794 unique potential combinations of symptoms that meet the diagnostic criteria; using *DSM-5* criteria, this rises to 636,120 combinations (Galatzer-Levy & Bryant, 2013). When actual profiles were measured in a large sample of individuals with diagnosed PTSD, there were 2,181 different patterns of symptoms (Bryant et al., 2022).

4.1. Limitations

The method of counting the number of times a model has been found to be the best-fitting in CFA analyses is subject to the limitation that it hinges on which models were selected for analysis. While this “vote-counting” method of review lacks the statistical rigor of meta-analyses of primary data, it complements meta-analysis. Rather than focusing on finding one model with superior mathematical fit indices, it demonstrated the thin margins between competing models. Comparison of fit indices between models was not an aim of this review, but it was noted qualitatively in most analyses that multiple models provided good or excellent mathematical fits and the difference between best and next-best models was slight, and often came down to judgement calls (e.g., (Charak et al., 2014; Mordeno et al., 2020; Sumner et al., 2015; Thomas et al., 2021)Charak, Armour, Elhai, Koot, et al., 2014; Elhai & Palmieri, 2011; Marshall et al., 2013; Mordeno et al., 2020; Sumner et al., 2015; Thomas et al., 2021), and two or more models tied for best fit twenty-three times. An example of a common interpretation was, “It is noteworthy, however, that the relative differences between various models on some of the fit indices were marginal and that all of the models tested met some of the standards outlined for good model fit” (Asmundson et al., 2000). In other words, the conclusions of most studies were

not between poor fitting models against good fitting models, but a relative difference between multiple good-fitting models.

A limitation of the third aim was that the ideal way to test differences between subpopulations may be to start with a theoretical model of why one subpopulation ought to have a different model of symptoms compared to the rest of the population. In contrast, as noted earlier, the studies that have been conducted were essentially samples of convenience (e.g., veterans, females, and nationality) because of the large sample sizes needed for factor analysis.

A limitation of the fourth aim is that external validation of factors that did not include EFA or CFA may not have been captured in our search method. Nevertheless, the full-text reviews of 204 studies did not reveal a body of literature with traction for understanding mechanisms underlying factors.

A possible limitation of the fifth aim is that we did not search beyond factor analysis studies for other types of studies that focused on symptom clusters for convergent, discriminant, or construct validity. While there are other types of studies that examined associations with a single gene (Pietrzak, Galea, et al., 2013) or brain imaging (Pietrzak, Henry, et al., 2013), those findings are preliminary in a small body of literature.

4.2. Conclusion

The overall aim was to examine whether the latent construct theory of factor analysis is appropriate for making decisions about PTSD diagnostic criteria. The five issues that were examined did not seem to support the usefulness of factor analysis because the findings are too disparate to be helpful. Namely, there is some evidence to support the four symptom clusters in the *DSM-5* as one useful model, but the overall evidence does not support it as the best or only useful model. Hence, as the revision process for *DSM* approaches, it may be appropriate to

revisit the *DSM-IV* model, question whether the *DSM-5* changes were critical to scientific advancements, and reconsider how factor analysis results are used to shape *DSM-6*.

Much effort has been devoted to test the fundamental premise of factor analysis that latent patterns in nature can be found that are too complex for other methods of measurement tools to detect. Our findings seem consistent with concerns about factor analysis for discovery in clinical psychology that has been voiced for almost as long as the technique has existed, including that the technique may be finding joints in nature that do not exist (Lykken, 1971; Schmitt et al., 2018) and/or that it is unlikely that factor analysis can represent the heterogeneity of natural organisms (Lykken, 1971).

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Data Availability

The dataset is available at the Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR) repository (record# [anonymized for blind review])

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Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram

Note: DSM = Diagnostic and Statistical Manual. CFA = confirmatory factor analysis. FA = either exploratory factor analysis or CFA. PTSD = posttraumatic stress disorder.

Fig. 2. Distribution of models that were discovered with EFA by the number of factors and by *DSM-IV* or *DSM-5* symptom sets. ● = analysis used *DSM-IV* symptoms. ■ = analysis used *DSM-5* symptoms.

Fig. 3. Distribution of models in adult samples that were concluded through CFA to be best-fitting, shown by symptom set and data collection method used. *DSM-IV* or *DSM-5* symptom sets. ● = *DSM-IV* symptoms, interview. ○ = *DSM-IV* symptoms, questionnaire. ▲ = *DSM-5* symptoms, interview. △ = *DSM-5* symptoms, questionnaire.

3.A. Adult samples.

3.B. Child and adolescent samples.

Fig. 4. Distribution of models that were concluded through CFA to be best-fitting shown by subpopulation on Y-axis: 1= male, 2 = female, 3 = Australia, 4 = Brazil, 5 = Canada, 6 = Chile, 7 = China, 8 = Germany, 9 = Holland, 10 = India, 11 = Philippines, 12 = Portugal, 13 = Poland, 14 = United State of America, 15 = help-seeking, 16 = combat trauma.

Fig. 5. Number of times one symptom cluster changed differentially relative to the other two clusters within one treatment arm. Y-axis: 0 = Cluster indicated on x-axis did not change while the other two clusters significantly decreased pre- to post-treatment; -1 = Cluster indicated on x-axis significantly decreased pre- to post-treatment while the other two clusters did not change. X-axis: 1 = Reexperiencing cluster, 2 = Avoidance Numbing cluster, 3 = Hyperarousal cluster, 4 = all three clusters changed or did not change in unison. Types of interventions: ● = antipsychotic medication, ■ = cognitive behavioral therapy, ◆ = eye movement desensitization and reprocessing, ▲ = prolonged exposure, x = placebo pill, ✕ = stress inoculation training, + = selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor, ○ = supportive psychotherapy, □ = topiramate, ◇ = trauma focused group, Δ = wait list.

